

Appendix Matters!

Hi Paul, do you have time to discuss an important matter?

Oh yes, Christie, please come.

Christie Nicholson is the Communications Manager in a small non-profit that works to promote access to educational materials and improve the quality of education internationally. She received a mail from a US-based for-profit Company indicating that the Appendix of one of the publications has “a significant amount of paraphrasing and exact language.”

Paul Smith is the program manager responsible for bringing out the publication. Paul is an expert in open licensing and developed this document with the help of two Consultants. The document was also discussed with a group of 20 experts in a workshop. The participants adapted the Appendix in question during the workshop.

“Christie, what is the matter?”

“Paul, this is about the Publication X that you brought last month. We have received a complaint that some of the information, especially the Appendix, does not attribute the source properly, and we do not have the requisite permission to use the same.”

“The Appendix is an adapted version of ‘document.pdf’ available on the University of Nowhere wiki page. The wiki page indicates that it is available under a CC BY-SA license. The ‘document.pdf’ is linked from this wiki page, and it also says that it was adapted from a checklist by our organization and that of the US-based Company. We have also indicated this clearly in our publication and attributed as such”, said Paul.

“So, is the source duly cited?” asked Christie.

“Yes, but we have not seen the document of the Company, and the ‘document.pdf’ indicates that they have used some information from our document and that of the Company,” said Paul. So, how do we respond to them? Christie asked.

“Our approach should be to tell the facts and ask what the way forward is?” said Paul.

“Thanks, Paul”, Christie said and left the room.

Paul, a conscientious professional and trainer, got worried about this issue considering the organizational reputation and immediately started to re-check. He then discussed the matter with the Technology Manager, an expert in copyrights and licensing. Paul explained the context and showed the links online to the Technology Manager. He said, “Paul, you have used the information from the University of Nowhere page, which is available in CC BY-SA. But the link ‘document.pdf’ does not show any license. However, this uses some of the materials available in CC BY-SA from our organization, as indicated in the acknowledgment. Therefore, the document should also be in the same license”.

Paul said, “I have said the same to Christie.”

“However, Paul, this is a serious issue, and the Company is trying to gauge our vulnerability. I believe this should be dealt with carefully and shared with our Executive Director immediately.” This conversation made Paul even more nervous, considering his position in the organization. Paul, anxious, tried to call his direct report, the Deputy Director, and then texted him to seek an early morning appointment. The next day, Paul met Krish Natarajan, his supervisor, and explained the matter. Krish said, “I am aware of the matter, and Christie brought this to my notice. You discuss this with Roma (Head of Administration), who will advise Christie to prepare an appropriate response.”

Paul then met Roma and explained the whole story of the publication and the sources of the link. Roma said, “In the appendix, we have given the link to the ‘document.pdf’ and indicated it as CC BY-SA. This is potentially an incorrect position, as I understand from the course, I took on licensing. Ideally, should not we have checked on this?”

“Yes, but since the main page was CC BY-SA and the ‘document.pdf’ was developed using some of our materials as indicated, we assumed CC BY-SA,” Paul said.

“Is not this we should have avoided?” asked Roma.

“I agree. You are saying the same thing I always say in my training programs. In this case, I can’t explain more why this happened”, said Paul apologetically. “It may be a good idea to revise this part and update this document.” “Maybe we can remove the present document from our website and then upload a revised version.”

After silence, “What is the way forward?” asked Paul.

“Tell Christie to share the mail with me, and I can help her prepare a response. We will discuss it with the Executive Director before sending a response”, Roma said.

Paul was not happy with himself and started feeling cornered, with no support for him, and in depression, started self-blame. Not only had he not slept the last night thinking about the consequences, but his concentration also deteriorated on other works the next day. It was a Friday, and he awaited with anxiety about the meeting with the Executive Director on Monday. Meanwhile, he used the content of the Appendix and scanned through plagiarism detection software and did not find substantial lifting from the source of the US-based Company, as initially claimed. On a deeper analysis, it was revealed that the framework used in the Appendix was different and could not be clearly said to have been adopted directly from the source as claimed.

Questions?

1. Is there a problem with the current attribution in the document?
2. Is there a violation of the rights of the US-based Company on the part of the non-profit?
3. Has the University of Nowhere violated any rights of the non-profit?
4. Is there a violation of CC BY-SA? If yes, by whom?

5. Can the US-based Company seek damages? What could be the extent of the claim?
6. Describe your views on this case and advise the Executive Director on the best way to resolve this issue.